

MERICS

Mercator Institute for China Studies

MERICS Europe-China Resilience Audit

The **MERICS Europe-China Resilience Audit** maps vulnerabilities and resilience across Europe in relation to China. It examines ten selected EU countries (Czechia, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Lithuania, Netherlands, Poland, Spain, Sweden) and the United Kingdom, building on a database featuring 98 indicators across four domains – economy, security, politics and society. The research is part of the project **“Dealing with a resurgent China”**, funded by the EU’s Horizon Europe research and innovation program.

picture alliance / Hans Lucas | Union
Européenne

Resilience Index overview

In recent years, China-related risks have become more apparent and acute for Europe. The discussion on how to manage those risks is at the heart of Europe’s adjustment of its China policy. To contribute to this process, this audit provides a comparative assessment, confirming significant differences in vulnerabilities and progress on resilience building measures towards China between the 11 countries covered.

[Read the analysis here](#)

Country profiles - vulnerability and resilience

Czechia's vulnerabilities increased, but remain comparatively low

France improved its resilience building across all four areas

Germany improved its security and political resilience

Hungary's vulnerabilities grew while resilience slightly declined

Italy boosted its security resilience through work on research security.

Lithuania's resilience continues to benefit from minimal exposure to China

The Netherlands cut security vulnerabilities,

Poland improved broadly but remains

Spain's resilience building process largely.

but made limited resilience gains

relatively vulnerable

stagnated

Sweden maintains gap in its economic resilience towards China

The UK improved its political and security resilience, but economic one lags

Publications

EU-China

Member
states' re-
silience ef-
forts fall
short of
looming
challenges:
Europe-
China
Resilience
Audit
Update 2025

Report
Oct 29,
2025

Grzegorz Stec

EU-China

Profiling
European
countries'
resilience
towards
China - 2025
Update

Esther Goreichy, Report
Grzegorz Stec, Oct 29,
Abigaël Vasselier 2025

EU-China

Honing the
“China
Reflex” that
allows
European
govern-
ments to
anticipate
and
respond

Comment
Oct 29,
2025

Grzegorz Stec

Industrial Policy and
Technology.
EU-China

Avoiding a
race to the
bottom: How
the EU can
counter
Chinese ex-
port controls

Comment
Oct 29,
Rebecca Arcesati 2025

Industrial Policy and
Technology.
Russia-China
Trade and Investment
EU-China

Europe's ve- hicle-data gap: How under-regu- lation gives Chinese car- makers an edge

Comment
Oct 29,
2025

Wendy Chang

EU-China

Europe's
blind spot:
How transna-
tional repres-
sion under-
mines demo-
cratic
resilience

Comment

Daria Impiombato Oct 29, 2025

EU-China

How Europe
is throwing
the strategic
communi-
cation game
with China
and how it
could go all
in

Comment
May 12,
2025

Grzegorz Stec

EU-China
Trade and Investment

Staying
united is the
best way for
the EU to re-
duce its
trade vulner-
abilities on
China

Comment
Mar 19,
François Chimits 2025

EU-China

The Europe-
China
Resilience
Audit:
Insights for
advancing
European
resilience

Report
Grzegorz Stec, Oct 31,
Helena Legarda 2024

EU-China

Profiling
European
countries'
resilience
towards
China

Report
Oct 31,
2024

EU-China Geopolitics

Europe's resilience vis-à-vis China, with Grzegorz Stec and Helena Legarda

Podcast
Nov 15, 2024

EU-China

European re-
silience will
require a
more proac-
tive approach
to
partnerships

Abigaël Vasselier, Comment
Helena Legarda Oct 31, 2024

EU-China

Building re-
silience: The
need for a
geopolitical
European
Commission
and strong
leadership
from Member
States

Abigaël Vasselier, Comment
Grzegorz Stec Oct 31, 2024

Project leads

Grzegorz

Stec

Head of
Brussels
Office/Senior
Analyst

Helena

Legarda

Head of
Program

Project contributors

Esther
Goreichy
Visiting Fellow

Eva
Seiwert
Senior
Analyst/Project
coordinator (on
parental leave)

Abigaël
Vasselier
Former
Director Policy
& European
Affairs/Former
Head of
Program
Foreign
Relations

Editors

Claudia
Wessling
Director
Communications
and
Publications

Mary
Hennock

Ellen
Thalman
External
freelance
editor

Funded by
the European Union

The MERICS EU-China Resilience Audit is part of the “Dealing with a Resurgent China” (DWARC) project, which has received funding from the European Union’s **Horizon Europe** research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 101061700.

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.